

Review Article

A brief review on endemic Corona Virus

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ABSTRACT

Corona virus causes respiratory infection including pneumonia, cold, sneezing and coughing while in animal it causes diarrhea and upper respiratory diseases. clinical perspective, adequate therapy should be provided based upon the underlying pathophysiological stage. When viral activity is the principal pathogenic factor, antiviral therapies will be most effective.

As per WHO and ECDC guideline avoid the contact with sick person and also avoid the market or public place as per possible. There are no anti corona virus vaccine to prevent or treatment but some supporting therapy work. Future research needed to fight with corona virus. Till only ‘Distance is rescue’.

Keywords: Corona virus, COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, etiology, Monoclonal antibody therapy

INTRODUCTION:

In December 2019, an outbreak of COVID-19—the disease caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) virus—occurred in Wuhan, China, rapidly leading to a global pandemic [1]. As the disease spreads, new information is emerging regarding the clinical course [2]. COVID-19 has three consecutive stages of increasing severity [3]. The early stage is characterized by infection with SARS-CoV-2. In this phase, flu-like symptoms can develop, mainly due to the viral infection itself. Subsequently, patients can develop viral pneumonia, requiring hospitalization, or even mechanical ventilation. The second stage is also characterized by pulmonary inflammation and coagulopathy, which can develop consecutively but often overlap. In addition, increased levels of inflammatory biomarkers such as C-reactive protein (CRP), ferritin, IL-6,

IL-1, and D-dimer are associated with the development of acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) and an unfavorable clinical course [3, 4].

The Virus:

Coronaviruses are single-stranded, positive-sense RNA viruses of the Coronaviridae family and Orthocoronavirinae subfamily that infect animals and humans. Coronaviruses are classified into four major genera: alphacoronavirus (α), betacoronavirus (β), gammacoronavirus (γ), and deltacoronavirus (δ)1. Currently, seven kinds of human coronaviruses have been identified, including HCoV 229E and HCoV NL63, which belong to the α genus; and HCoV-OC43, HCoV-VHKU1, SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV, and SARSCoV-2, which belong to the β genus.

Figure 1. Structure of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). **A**, Viral particles in ultrathin sections under the electron microscope at 200 kV. Chinese name: 2019-nCoV Wuhan strain 02 (English name: C-F13-nCoV Wuhanstrain 02). **B**, SARS-CoV-2 pattern diagram: SARS-CoV-2 includes a single-stranded, positive-sense RNA and four structural proteins: the spike protein (S), envelope protein (E), membrane protein (M), and nucleocapsid protein. Note: the picture in Figure 1A was obtained from the National Pathogen Microbial Resource Bank at the China Center for Disease Control and Prevention (NPRC: 2020.00002).

Transmission — Person-to-person spread is the main mode of SARS-CoV-2 transmission. It is thought to occur mainly through close-range contact (ie, within approximately six feet or two meters) via respiratory particles; virus released in the respiratory secretions when a person with infection coughs, sneezes, or talks can infect another person if it is inhaled or makes direct contact with the mucous membranes. Infection might also occur if a person's hands are contaminated by these secretions or by touching contaminated surfaces and then they touch their eyes, nose, or mouth, although contaminated surfaces are not thought to be a major route of transmission. Corona virus is spherical or pleomorphic, single stranded, enveloped RNA and covered with club shaped glycoprotein. Corona viruses are four sub types such as alpha, beta, gamma and delta corona virus. Each of sub type corona viruses has many serotypes. Some of them were affect human of other affected animals such as pigs, birds, cats, mice and dogs.[6–10]

Corona virus was isolated from bronchoalveolar lavage fluid in china in 2020. It is also detected in blood samples. Till now, corona virus was not confirmed in feces and urine sample of patient.[11–13]

The novelty and high infectivity of COVID-19 requires extra biosafety measures, including appropriate personal and environmental protective equipment.

Histopathology

The predominant pathology in the lungs of deceased patients with COVID-19 is diffuse alveolar damage (DAD).(25-38)

This pattern of acute lung injury is the histologic finding observed in patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome regardless of the etiology. Detection of SARS-CoV-2 RNA in blood has also been reported in some but not all studies that have tested for it [14-18].

The risk of transmission from an individual who is asymptomatic appears less than that from one who is symptomatic [19-24].

RESULTS:

Laboratory tests indicate decreased absolute lymphocyte counts in most patients, suggesting that SARS-CoV-2 may act on lymphocytes in a similar way as SARS. Patients frequently present lymphopenia (70.3%), prolonged coagulation (58%), and increased lactate dehydrogenase levels (39.9%)²⁷. White blood cells, hemoglobin, and platelets are lower than the normal range in some patients¹⁷, while C-reactive protein and erythrocyte sedimentation rate are elevated⁽³⁹⁻⁴⁰⁾.

Fig. 2 —79-year-old woman who presented with chest pain, cough, and fever for 3 days. Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) had recently been diagnosed in two of her household members. Patient developed acute respiratory distress syndrome within subsequent few days and died 11 days after admission. (Courtesy of Song F, Shanghai Public Health Clinical Center, Shanghai, China) CT image

After screening the titles and abstracts for eligibility, 116 potentially relevant full-text articles were screened, 74 of which were excluded. No additional articles were retrieved after screening the references in the included articles and excluded reviews. Thus, a total of 42 case reports and case series were included in our systematic review [39-83].

Computed tomography (CT) shows shadows or frosted glass opacity in the lung in most COVID-19 patients⁽⁸⁴⁾. Clinically relevant indicators of the disease that significantly deviate from normal values (including oxygen saturation, respiratory rate, white blood cell/lymphocyte count, and chest X-ray/CT findings) predict poor clinical outcomes⁽⁸⁵⁾.

Bioinformatic analysis has proposed baricitinib as a potential drug that may inhibit SARS-CoV-2⁽⁸⁶⁾.

Monoclonal antibody therapy refers to the extraction of memory B cells from patients in the recovery stage, which then produce specific antibodies for antiviral therapy given to patients not recovered. Monoclonal antibodies can be obtained by cloning antibody genes from a small number of memory B cells that have neutralizing and specific effects. Studies have shown that monoclonal antibody treatment can significantly reduce the mortality of patients infected with Ebola virus⁽⁸⁷⁾. Monoclonal antibody therapy has become a focus of research for COVID-19 treatment.

CONCLUSION:

The authors did not find a significant relationship between overall large airway inflammation and intubation, or bacterial or fungal pneumonia.⁽³⁷⁾

From a clinical perspective, adequate therapy should be provided based upon the underlying pathophysiological stage. When viral activity is the principal pathogenic factor, antiviral therapies will be most effective. In the vascular stage, directed anti-inflammatory, anticoagulant, and/or anticomplement agents are indicated. Finally, when fibrosis is developing biologicals and/or small-molecule antifibrotic compounds—even those in the experimental stage—should be considered. Currently, in clinical practice a patient's precise pathophysiological state cannot be determined by tissue biopsy, and clinical insight relies upon circumstantial evidence such as RT-PCR to detect viral RNA, laboratory measurements of cytokines and

inflammatory markers, and radiological evaluation.(88)

Organ damages are caused either directly by the virus via the angiotensin converting enzyme 2 receptor or indirectly by the cytokine storm that induces an immune system dysregulation with an activation of the coagulation cascade responsible for disseminated intravascular coagulation and thus multiple organ failure. Further studies are warranted to further understand the pathogenesis of COVID-19.(89)

In other published studies, the most common findings on follow-up CT included increased consolidative opacities and loss of crazy paving pattern. Progression of GGO has been reported as an interval change in the early days after symptomatic presentation. Development of pleural effusions as well as progression to a mixed pattern of GGO and consolidative opacities have been reported in later disease stages [90-92].

Some authors found no significant pathological changes in the heart of patients deceased from COVID-19 infection [20]. Tian. S et al [35]

Lung damages can be caused either directly by the SARS-CoV-2 via the ACE2 receptor or indirectly by cytokine storm which is linked to an excessively exaggerated and uncontrolled immune response (93,94).

revealed no inflammatory cellular infiltration in the endocardium and myocardium of their four patients. However, they found irregularly shaped myocardial cells with darkened cytoplasm. The pathological changes were not sufficient for interpretation as acute myocardial injury. They found, as well, various degrees of focal edema, interstitial fibrosis, and myocardial hypertrophy but they were attributed to the patients' underlying diseases. Xu. Z et al [95] revealed that the only substantial pathological change in the heart was the presence of few interstitial mononuclear inflammatory infiltrate. On the contrary, all three cases in the study of Yao. XH et al [96] showed hypertrophy, degeneration and necrosis of some myocardial cells, mild interstitial hyperemia, edema,

infiltration of a small number of lymphocytes, monocytes and neutrophils. This study performed also Immunohistochemical staining, electron microscopy examination and RTPCR detection of the SARS-CoV-2 in all three heart tissue samples. They showed that the inflammatory cells infiltrating the myocardium were mainly macrophages and a small number were of CD4-positive T lymphocytes. No CD8-positive T lymphocytes or CD20-positive B lymphocytes were seen. Ultrastructural study showed myocardial fibers swelling and dissolution. Immunohistochemical staining and PCR detection did not identify SARS-CoV-2 component in myocardial tissue [96].

Another finding reported is abundant intra-alveolar neutrophilic infiltration consistent with bronchopneumonia of a superimposed bacterial infection [98,99].

Yao. XH et al [96] reported some pathological changes in the gastrointestinal system including partial epithelial degeneration and necrosis, dilatation and congestion of lamina propria and submucosal small blood vessels with infiltration of lymphocytes, monocytes, and plasma cells. Xiao. F et al [97] found no significant damage in the epithelium lining the mucosa of esophagus, stomach, duodenum, and rectum. They observed also an infiltrate of occasional lymphocytes in esophageal squamous epithelium as well as numerous infiltrating plasma cells and lymphocytes with interstitial edema in lamina propria of the stomach, duodenum, and rectum. The viral nucleocapsid protein was visualized.

As per WHO and ECDC guideline avoid the contact with sick person and also avoid the market or public place as per possible. There are no anti corona virus vaccine to prevent or treatment but some supporting therapy work. Future research needed to fight with corona virus. Till only 'Distance is rescue'.(100)

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